

Supporting information

Fe-MOF Catalytic Nanoarchitectonic toward Electrochemical Ammonia Production

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Figure S1. (A) SEM image of pristine PCN-250-Fe₃ MOF sample. (B-E) EDS mapping of elements.

Figure S2. Deconvoluted O 1s XPS spectra of pristine PCN-250-Fe₃ MOF sample.

Figure S3. (A) SEM image of Fe MOF catalyst post electrocatalytic experiments. EDS mapping of (B) Fe, (C) N, (D) C, (E) O elements.

Table S1. Nitrate to ammonia conversion results using various Fe based catalysts.

Material	NH ₃ FE / Potential	Yield rate	Electrolyte conditions	Reference
Fe single-atom catalysts (Fe-PPy SACs)	~100% at -0.7 V vs RHE	2.75 mg _{NH₃} h ⁻¹ cm ⁻² at -0.7 V vs RHE	0.1 M KOH/ 0.1 M KNO ₃	1
2D Fe-based cyano-coordination polymer nanosheets (Fe-cyano NSs)	~90.4% at -0.5 V vs RHE	42.1 mg h ⁻¹ mg _{cat} ⁻¹ at -0.5 V vs RHE	1 M KOH/ 0.1 M KNO ₃	2
Fe-doped Co ₃ O ₄ nanoarray	95.5% at -0.7 V vs RHE	0.624 mg mg _{cat} ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ at -0.7 V vs RHE	0.1 M PBS/ 50 mM NO ₃ ⁻	3
Atomically dispersed FeMo-N-C SAC catalyst	94.7% at -0.45 V vs RHE	18.0 μmol cm ⁻² h ⁻¹	0.05 M PBS/ 0.16 M KNO ₃	4
Fe ₁ /NC at 900 °C	86% at -0.7 V vs RHE	18.8 mg _{NH₃} h ⁻¹ mg _{cat} ⁻¹ at -0.9 V	0.1 M K ₂ SO ₄ / 0.5 M KNO ₃	5
Single-atom Fe-doped V ₂ O ₅	97.1% at -0.7 V vs RHE	12.5 mg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻² at -0.7 V	1 M KOH/ 0.1 M KNO ₃	6
Cu-Fe bimetallic catalysts (Cu ₅ Fe ₅ /OMC)	~70% at -0.5 V vs RHE	365.9 μg h ⁻¹ mg _{cat} ⁻¹ at -0.8 V vs RHE	0.1 M PBS/ 500 ppm KNO ₃	7
Fe single atom catalyst	~75% at -0.66 V vs RHE	~20,000 μg h ⁻¹ mg _{cat} ⁻¹ at -0.85 V vs RHE	0.5 M KNO ₃ / 0.10 M K ₂ SO ₄	8
Co-doped Fe/Fe ₂ O ₃	85.2 ± 0.6% at -0.75 V vs RHE	1,505.9 ± 130.5 μg h ⁻¹ cm ⁻² at -0.95 V vs. RHE	0.1 M Na ₂ SO ₄ with NaNO ₃	9
PCN-250-Fe ₃ MOF (Activated)	~90% at -1 V vs. RHE	2.5 x 10 ⁻⁴ mol cm ⁻² h ⁻¹ at -1 V vs. RHE	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄ / 0.1 M KNO ₃	This work

Figure S4. Cluster models of PCN-250. A) Model with all three Fe atoms in oxidation state +III. The OH^- group is added to maintain the system neutral. B) Model with two Fe atoms in oxidation state +III and one Fe atom in oxidation state +II. Carbon atoms are grey, oxygen red, iron orange and hydrogen white.

Figure S5. Possible reaction pathways of the NO_3^- reduction reaction based on the study of Wu et al.³⁴ catalyzed by PCN-250 represented as a $\text{Fe}_3(\text{III})\text{OH}$ model (Figure S4A) in the gas phase. Numbers under/next to arrows are reaction energies (ΔE) in eV. Reaction pathway marked by green arrows is depicted in Figure 6 and discussed in the main text.

Figure S6. A) The reaction mechanism of the NRA catalyzed by the PCN-250 (Fe₂(III)Fe(II) model). Brown values are reaction energies (ΔE_R) in the gas phase, blue values in water. B) Diagram of the NRA reaction energies. The multiplicities (M) of species are also reported. Carbon atoms are grey, oxygen red, nitrogen blue, iron orange and hydrogen white.

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